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INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI**

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УЗБЕКИСТАНА ИМЕНИ МИРЗО УЛУГБЕКА**

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BIOTEXNOLOGIYANING RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI VA MUAMMOLARI
ROLE OF STAPHYLOCOCCUS HAEMOLYTICUS AND ANTIBIOTIC
RESISTANCE IN VAGINAL AEROBIC VAGINITIS

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Abstract: *Staphylococcus haemolyticus* (*S. haemolyticus*) is one of the predominant bacterial species found in aerobic vaginitis (AV) microbiota. This bacterium has a higher level of antibiotic resistance than coagulase-negative staphylococci, which makes it a clinically important pathogen. Studies have shown that *S. haemolyticus* has the ability to transfer antibiotic resistance genes to other staphylococcal species, which complicates antibiotic therapy. In addition, this bacterium is not only associated with aerobic vaginitis, but can also cause severe infections such as meningitis, prostatitis, urinary tract infections, and otitis media, especially in immunocompromised patients. In women, *S. haemolyticus* has been shown to cause dysbiosis of the vaginal microbiota, increase inflammatory processes, and promote the growth of other pathogenic microorganisms. This study evaluated the antibiotic susceptibility of *S. haemolyticus* strains associated with aerobic vaginitis and investigated their pharmacological properties. The results obtained confirm the high level of antibiotic resistance of *S. haemolyticus* and its clinical significance, and are of great importance in the development of AV treatment strategies.

Keywords: *S. haemolyticus*, antibiotic resistant, virulence.

Coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS) constitute the major microbiota of aerobic vaginitis [1]. These pathogens are under-recognized and precise species identification is not performed in many microbiology laboratories [3]. Clinical CoSS accounts for 10–20% of infections. In recent years, various investigators have described the increasing frequency of multidrug-resistant strains of *S. haemolyticus* [4]. *S. haemolyticus* is more resistant to antibiotics than any other CoSS, with the broadest spectrum of resistance observed among strains isolated from hospital settings. The presence of resistance genes in *S. haemolyticus* and its spread in hospital settings pose a potential risk, as this bacterium can harbor resistance genes and transfer them to other species. *S. haemolyticus* isolated from aerobic vaginitis in women showed high resistance to various antibiotic classes. *S. haemolyticus* exhibits resistance to multiple antibiotic classes, including beta-lactams and fluoroquinolones, making treatment challenging.

The results of the chart show that *S. haemolyticus* is highly resistant to beta-lactam and fluoroquinolone antibiotics. This resistance may make it difficult for the bacteria to respond to antibiotic therapy. This increases the likelihood that it will cause significant clinical problems in the treatment of infections. In conclusion, this bacterium can exacerbate various inflammatory processes in women and pose difficulties in treatment due to its resistance to antibiotics. This situation indicates the need to improve infection control strategies.

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